

D1.2

Data Management Plan

D1.2	Data Management Plan
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Disclaimer

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Abbreviations

DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
RP	Reporting period
T	Task
TWG	Thematic Working Group
WP	Work Package

Introduction to the project

BOOST4BIOEAST is a Coordination and Support Action funded by the European Commission developed to support the BIOEAST Initiative with the aim of empowering national stakeholders in the Central Eastern European and Baltic countries for the development of national bioeconomy action plans and to build long-lasting structures and spaces of dialogue for national and macro-regional cooperation. The project will enrich knowledge on the bioeconomy and stimulate related research and innovation across the macro-region.

Executive summary

To ensure sound and ethical data management throughout the project, the first version of BOOST4BIOEAST's Data Management Plan lays out the general methodological principles pertaining to the management of the data that will be generated and/or collected within the framework of the project. Additionally, it offers an initial summary of the data to be collected, together with details on the technique for managing the data and ensuring that it is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). Findability and interoperability are ensured thanks to the definition of an official naming convention, the use of repositories to store the datasets, and the standard rules and prescriptions concerning the deliverables and its associated data. Furthermore, BOOST4BIOEAST Microsoft SharePoint platform brings the collaboration among consortium partners to its maximum potential. Moreover, aspects such as the data security, ethics, resource allocation or evolution during the project are also tackled in the deliverable.

This is the first version of the Data Management Plan, it will be regularly revisited throughout the duration of the project and reviewed at reporting periods (M18 and M36). The final version will be presented in D1.3 at M36.

1 Introduction

The present document is the first draft of the Data Management Plan (DMP), which is elaborated as a deliverable (D1.2) within the BOOST4BIOEAST project. In order to reflect an accurate and comprehensive plan for managing the data collected and/or generated by the project, both during and after the completion of BOOST4BIOEAST, it will function as a living document that is updated and further elaborated during the course of the project.

At the core of the project, there is the need to establish or improve national bioeconomy expert communities (BIOEAST HUBs) as focal points of capacity building and catalyst for stakeholder engagement at national level to support policymaking through participatory processes. The HUBs will be engaged in the development of national bioeconomy action plans, and in fostering national bioeconomy innovation ecosystems through cross-sectoral collaboration, capacity building and facilitating access to knowledge and networks to all bioeconomy stakeholders. Furthermore, at macro-regional level, they will contribute to the work of seven BIOEAST Thematic Working Groups (TWGs) in updating the BIOEAST Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda.

This will be achieved through the implementation of a set of coordination and support actions:

- Build on and connect with already existing clusters, initiatives, and projects (WP2, 6, 7, 8),
- Engage stakeholders from all bioeconomy related sectors, including policymakers in the HUB and TWG activities (WP2, 6),
- Carry out multidimensional assessments: mapping of bioeconomy competences, biomass availability, educational needs, materials available and innovation systems (WP3, 4, 5),
- Develop the BIOEAST Knowledge Platform to collect, store and make available bioeconomy-related knowledge for stakeholders (WP5),
- Organise an Open Innovation Challenge followed up by pitching events and expand the BIOEAST UniNet (WP4 and 5),
- Support the efficient monitoring and reporting of WPs, HUBs and TWGs (WP1, 6).

BOOST4BIOEAST will gather a great variety of data through surveys (*T2.2, T3.3*), interviews (*T2.1, T4.1, T5.2*), workshops and webinars (*T3.4, T4.2, T5.2, T6.2, T7.2, T7.3, T7.4, T8.1, T8.3*), HUB and TWG meetings (*T2.2, T2.3, T6.1, T6.3*). BOOST4BIOEAST will also generate other types of research outputs, such as capacity-building materials (*T2.2*), monitoring frameworks (*T1.4, T6.4*), results from the multi-dimensional analysis (*T3.3, T4.1, T5.1*), action plans (*WP7*) and strategies (*WP6*). Most of these activities involve external (non-project) participants and collect personal data (mainly names, institutes, country).

The consortium has compiled this DMP by considering the requirements provided in the Grant Agreement (GA) and in accordance with the guidelines on FAIR principles.

2 Data summary

In BOOST4BIOEAST project, 27 out of 29 deliverables are public (see Appendix I). In addition, a data summary table has been created to collect all the different types of data generated at WP level for which the table components are presented in Appendix II most of which is accessible to the whole consortium on the project's SharePoint. Table 1 outlines an overview of the datasets that is planned to be generated within BOOST4BIOEAST, according to preliminary inputs to the data summary table provided by WP and task leaders in M6. It is important to note that while most datasets outlined in the table are for the use of "Consortium only", we will make sure to provide additional public outputs in the next version of the DMP in RP1.

Table 1. Data summary based on preliminary inputs from WPs

Dataset title	Responsible partner	Target user	Personal data	Type of data	Format	Data sharing rules
WP1						
List of consortium contacts	ÖMKI	consortium	YES	excel file	.xls	Consortium only
WP Logframes	ÖMKI	consortium	YES	excel file	.xls	Consortium only
BIOEAST Board contact list	ÖMKI	consortium	YES	excel file	.xls	Consortium only
Data summary table	ÖMKI	consortium	YES	excel file	.xls	Consortium only
Risk register	ÖMKI	consortium	YES	excel file	.xls	Consortium only
Project meeting minutes	ÖMKI	consortium	YES	text file	.doc	Consortium only
Financial management	SIE	consortium	YES	excel file	.xls	Consortium only
WP2						
HUB Coordinator contacts	BME	stakeholders	YES	excel file	.xls	Public
Contacts of members of 11 BIOEAST HUBs	HUB Coordinators	HUB Coordinators, HUB members	YES	excel file	.xls	HUB Coordinators and HUB members only
HUB Coordination Body meeting minutes	BME	HUB coordinators	YES	text file	.doc; .pdf	Consortium only
HUB kick-off meetings participants	BME	HUB Coordination team	YES	excel file	.xls; .pdf	Consortium only
Annual BIOEAST Bioeconomy Conferences (3) registered participants	BME	consortium	YES	excel file	.xls; .pdf	Consortium only
Survey results of capacity needs of public administration officials and research organisations	CC	consortium	YES	text file	.doc	Consortium only
Capacity building material	CC	consortium	NO	text file	.doc; .pdf	Public
Participants of the capacity building courses	CC	consortium	YES	excel file	.xls	Consortium only
List of participants of inter-ministerial group meetings	CR HUB	consortium	YES	excel file	.xls	Consortium only

Dataset title	Responsible partner	Target user	Personal data	Type of data	Format	Data sharing rules
WP3						
Long list of indicators	DBFZ, BME	HUB Coordinators	NO	text + excel file	.doc; .xls	Consortium only
Surveys responses: prioritisation	DBFZ, BME	HUB Coordinators	NO	excel file	.csv; .xls	Consortium only
Bioeconomy-related competencies and biomass indicators	DBFZ	HUBs, national policymakers	NO	excel file	.csv; .xls	Consortium only
WP4						
Interview materials (templates, transcripts)	AKI	consortium	YES	text file	.doc	Consortium only
Mapped institutions database	AKI	consortium	NO	excel file	.csv; .xls	Consortium only
Mapped initiatives database	AKI	consortium	NO	excel file	.csv; .xls	Consortium only
HORIZON projects database	AKI	consortium	NO	excel file	.csv; .xls	Consortium only
List of solution providers for the OIC	EFI	consortium	NO	excel file	.csv; .xls	Consortium only
WP5						
Database of educational materials	EFI	consortium	YES	excel file	.csv; .xls	Consortium only
Personal data of people signing up webforms	Trust-IT / COMMpla	Consortium + external users	YES	excel file	.xls	Restricted to owning partners only
WP6						
TWG + HUB Logframes	ÖMKi + TWG + HUB Coordinators	consortium	YES	excel file	.xls	Consortium only
(Contact) list of participant stakeholders on science-policy dialogues	AKI	consortium	YES	excel file	.xls	Consortium only
Guidelines for science-policy dialogues	AKI	consortium	NO	text files	.doc; .pdf	Consortium only
Summary of science-policy dialogues	TWG Coordinators, AKI	policymakers, scientists, consortium	NO	text files	.doc; .pdf	Open to public
WP7						
List of participants of the workshops	4CF	consortium	YES	excel file	.xlsx	Consortium only
Collected inputs from WP3-5	ÖMKi	HUBs	NO	text and excel file	.doc, .xls	Consortium only
Recordings of workshops	ÖMKi	HUBs	YES	Multimedia	Mp4, mov	Consortium only
Results of cross-fertilisation workshops	TTK	consortium	NO	text file	.doc; .pdf	Consortium only

Dataset title	Responsible partner	Target user	Personal data	Type of data	Format	Data sharing rules
WP8						
Final conference participants list	APRE + ÖMKI	consortium	YES	excel file	.xls	Consortium only
Contact list of Communication Expert Teams (CET)	Trust-IT / COMMpla	consortium	YES	excel file	.xls	Consortium only
Subscriptions to project newsletter	APRE	APRE	YES	excel file	.xls	Restricted to owning partners
Newsletters and press releases	APRE, ÖMKI	interested stakeholders	NO	word files	.doc .pdf	Public
MailChimp access code	APRE	APRE	NO	e-mail	e-mail	Restricted to owning partners
Access to social media account	APRE	APRE	NO	word file	.doc	Restricted to owning partners
Project collaborations	APRE	APRE	NO	excel file	.xls	Consortium only
Mutual learning workshop participants	APRE	APRE	YES	excel file	.xls	Consortium only
International policy dialogues participants	DBFZ, HUB Coordinators	DBFZ	YES	excel file	.xls	Consortium only
WP9						
NDA between ÖMKI and Privanova (Ethics advisor)	ÖMKI	consortium	YES	text file	.doc; .pdf	Consortium only

3 FAIR data

The Guidelines on Data Management (European Commission, 2022) emphasise the importance of making the data produced by projects funded under Horizon Europe FAIR, with a view to ensuring its sound management. This means using standards and metadata to make data discoverable, specifying data sharing procedures and which data will be open, allowing data exchange via open repositories as well as facilitating the reusability of the data.

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

The partners of the project share data between partners in the “BOOST4BIOEAST” Microsoft SharePoint. BOOST4BIOEAST places special emphasis on enhancing the discoverability of the data collected/ generated during the course of its activities. In generating metadata, naming documents in a standardised, logical, and intuitive way enables partners to discover and manage project datasets when needed. BOOST4BIOEAST supports the sharing of information consortium-wide and therefore suggests a uniform naming convention for all project-generated datasets. In doing so, project partners can easily identify a file as well as classify and sort them. At the same time, versioning should be part of a naming convention to clearly identify the changes and edits in a file. The naming convention is described below.

[Name of project] _ [Name of Report] _ [WPX] _ [Issue Date] _ [Version number]

- Name of project: BOOST4BIOEAST
- Name of Report: A short version of the name of the activity for which the dataset is created.
- WPX: An indication of the WP assigned to the dataset.
- Issue Date: The date on which the latest version of the dataset was modified (DD/MM/YYYY).

Moreover, a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) will be assigned to published articles, acting as a unique and permanent code to identify the publication.

3.2 Making data accessible

3.2.1 Repository: storing and sharing data and other outputs with project partners

The collected data and information are stored and shared with project partners in the project's SharePoint. This is suitable for shared short-term storage of data and resources during the project. Each partner is in charge of uploading the data gathered and produced in their project activities on shared folders of respective WPs. Only members of the consortium, after validation from the administrator (Coordinators) can access this space. Data and resources collected for internal purposes will be stored in secure local repositories of the organisation responsible for collecting them and will be retained for 5 years after the end of the project.

3.2.2 Open availability of data and other outputs

According to Article 17 "Communication, dissemination, open science and visibility" in the GA, "each beneficiary must disseminate their results as soon as feasible, in a publicly available format, subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests". The data will be made accessible following the accessibility criteria:

- Restricted data (owning partner only): accessible by the owner only, deposited in the repository of the owner partner. Data must be kept for at least 5 years after the project ends.
- Consortium data (project partners only): accessible by the consortium members only, deposited in the BOOST4BIOEAST SharePoint. Data must be kept for at least 5 years after the project ends.
- Open data (public): accessible by the public, wherever possible, data will be published in a trusted repository to ensure open access in line with the requirements of the GA. When selecting an archive, we aim to meet the following criteria:
 - The data can be given a persistent identifier (e.g., DOI);
 - Data and metadata are accessible through a data repository such as Zenodo.

Moreover, the project will make the public outputs from the project available through the BIOEAST website's (www.bieast.hu) Knowledge Platform developed in M7. News will be shared

via the website, newsletter and social media channels (LinkedIn, X and Facebook). The data will be openly accessible to anyone interested.

Scientific peer-reviewed publications are not specifically included to be generated by the project. However, if they are produced, according to Article 17 of GA “beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results”. These publications will be submitted to open-access journals to ensure immediate open access and deposited in a trusted repository. The following ones are the main publishing routes, which are adapted by BOOST4BIOEAST, and are explained in Figure 1 below.

- Green open access: also known as self-archiving, this process entails the author archiving their published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript in an online repository so that the public can freely access it. The publisher typically owns the copyright to these publications and there are limitations on how the work may be re-used. The rules and conditions, such as which article version may be re-used and when the article can be made publicly accessible in the repository (embargo period), are set forth in the specific self-archiving policies of each journal or publisher.
- Gold open access: the final version of an article is freely and permanently accessible for the public, immediately after publication. Authors maintain the copyright for the article and most of the restrictions on permission are removed.

Figure 1. Open access of publications and research data (source: European Commission)

Furthermore, Article 16 of the GA establishes that the ownership of the results belongs to the beneficiary who generates them, which includes the research data produced during the project.

It will be jointly shared if two or more partners have participated in the production of the research data.

Important remark for any partner intending to disseminate its non-public results: it is obligatory to provide notice, with sufficient information on the dissemination contents, to other partners at least 45 days in advance of the dissemination, according to Article 16 of the GA. The beneficiaries may object within 30 days of receiving, if they can show that the transfer would adversely affect their access rights. In this case, appropriate steps to solve the conflicts should take place; otherwise, the dissemination would not be able to further proceed.

3.2.3 Handling and publishing personal data

The rights of participants will be respected in line with ethical guidelines, and applicable EU and national legal frameworks for data protection, as well as international human rights norms and frameworks. Personal data will be collected only to the degree that is necessary for the implementation of the project. Data processing will be subject to appropriate safeguards:

- data will be processed in anonymised or pseudo-anonymised form where relevant,
- data processing will be subject to free and fully informed consent of the persons concerned,
- the data subjects will be made aware that they take part in the project and be informed of their legal rights to their data.

3.3 Making data interoperable

Data and other outputs are stored and shared in different formats depending on their type and the software used to produce them. However, their (re)usability is ensured by using formats that are widely used, preferably non-proprietary formats. Already during the project, data will be stored in a format that is easily accessible to other project participants. In BOOST4BIOEAST, most of the data will be enclosed in text documents or in excel sheets. Therefore, most of the data will be presented in .docx, .txt, .pdf, and .xlsx formats. Public data will be shared in repositories/archives mainly in commonly used formats to ensure the interoperability and re-usability of our data.

3.4 Data re-use

Data reusability means the ease with which data can be re-used for further research or other purposes. In the project, 27 out of 29 deliverables are public (see Appendix I), not subjected to an embargo period and therefore can be reused from its publication. According to preliminary inputs to the data summary table (Table 1) provided by WP and task leaders in M6, the other dataset - besides the public deliverables - planned to be open to the public and therefore have permit for re-use is the "Summary of science-policy dialogues" (WP6), contacts of HUB Coordinators (WP2), capacity building materials (WP2) and newsletters & press releases (WP8). Further public outputs are planned to be provided for the next version of the DMP at M36.

The Consortium is committed to keeping the data usable for as long as feasible following the project's completion. An initial duration of 5 years has been set.

4 Allocation of resources

BOOST4BIOEAST has not identified any specific costs associated with data management between partners. The external data sharing through websites and newsletters are budgeted under WP5 and WP8 activities. Daily data management procedures are covered by the project budget as salary costs and the equipment used like archives and data repositories, which are used to make data and other outputs publicly available, are provided at no cost. There are also no fees for partners using the project's SharePoint.

Future version of the DMP will be updated by partners being asked to provide information about whether they have resources planned in the project budget for:

- data accessibility (such as publication fees in open access journals in case they plan to publish);
- long-term preservation of the data, even after the end of the project.

5 Data security

As mentioned above, BOOST4BIOEAST project uses Microsoft's SharePoint (named "BOOST4BIOEAST") as the repository to manage, share, and collaborate on the data and documents related to the project. Microsoft SharePoint enforces two-factor authentication and encryption of data in transit and at rest. Files are stored in SharePoint and are protected by SharePoint encryption (Microsoft SharePoint, 2022). Therefore, Microsoft SharePoint follows all the security practices and procedures to assure a safe collaborative working platform. Each partner is responsible for uploading the data gathered and produced in their project activities on the SharePoint WP folders.

The project's data security aims at minimising the probability of the occurrence of data breach during the course and after the completion of the project. Particularly, in case of personal data collection / generation, it is crucial that this data can only be accessed by those authorised to do so. Access to closed data in the shared folder will only be permitted to authorised project partners.

All project partners are responsible for processing data using appropriate means, such as private servers or cloud service providers that adhere to the relevant legal data protection requirements such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (European Parliament and Council, 2016) and will ensure that this data is protected, and any necessary data security controls have been implemented, to minimise the risk of information leak and destruction. This case refers to the data that will be closed and therefore will not be shared and / or re-used within the framework of the project.

Deliverable 9.1 OEI – Requirement no. 1 (Ethics) introduced an additional level of monitoring to the overall data protection management component of the project by partners asked to keep their internal Data Protection Officers (DPOs) (if any) apprised of their organisation's involvement in the BOOST4BIOEAST project. Contact information of the DPOs or the privacy policy of the data controller of partners can be found in D9.1.

6 Ethics

To ensure that all ethical aspects are considered and that the BOOST4BIOEAST project is compliant with all legal requirements and ethical issues, a general strategy has been designed by the Ethics Requirements (OEI – Requirement no. 1) that is defined in D9.1 of WP9. The project will process personal data including the possibility of processing special categories of personal data. The lawfulness of processing personal data will rely on the participants' informed, freely given, and unambiguous consent. Personal data processing mainly concerns contact details and stakeholders' and experts' opinions who will participate in the project activities.

7 Conclusion

The present document describes the data management activities of the BOOST4BIOEAST project and emphasises the importance of effective data management in achieving project objectives. By following this DMP, BOOST4BIOEAST can ensure the efficient and responsible management of data generated by project partners, maximising the impact and value of its outcomes and promoting collaboration and knowledge exchange within the BIOEAST community.

Being a living document, the DMP is updated as the project progresses, taking into account the most recent results. By the time the project is finished, it should have undergone at least two updates at reporting periods (M18 and M36) and the final DMP will be presented in D1.3 (M36).

8 References

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9 Appendices

Appendix I. Overview of data summary table components

Data denomination	
Data title	Short and descriptive title of the dataset or research output which should be easily searchable and findable
Related WP and task	Related WP and task numbers
Dataset vs. research output	Dataset (e.g. list of contact, list of mapped projects, answers gathered from surveys, registrations including external (non-project) participants for meetings etc.), Research outputs (e.g. project reports, project related articles, documents). Other research outputs (e.g. software used, codes etc)
Responsible partner(s) for generating the data	Names of partner institutes
Personal data	To explicitly state if personal data is included or not
Re-use	Data can be publicly re-used for further research or other purposes
Data type included	Name, country, institution, position, e-mail address etc.
Creator(s) name(s) and institute	Authors responsible for the creation of the dataset or research output, and their affiliation
Delivery	Date of expected delivery
Purpose	
Target user	Consortium, researchers, policymakers, practitioners, citizens, etc.
Purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project	Short description of the aim of the (data) generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project
Specifications	
Type of data	Type of data contained in the data set
Qualitative or quantitative data	The data generated is only quantitative, qualitative or includes both
Data generation software	MS Excel, MS Word etc.
Format	This could be CSV, DOC, HTML, etc.
Size	The approximate size of the data set, MB/GB/TB
Access	
Data storage location	e.g. data is stored on BOOST4BIOEAST SharePoint, partner local repository, etc.
Data sharing rules	- restricted (owning partner only) - consortium (project partners only) - open (public)
Explanation	Explanation in case it will not be public
Embargo	Duration of embargo foreseen for a data set

Appendix II. List of BOOST4BIOEAST Deliverables

D no.	Deliverable title	Due (M)	WP	Beneficiary	Diss. level
D1.1	Risk Management Plan	6	WP1	1 - ÖMKI	Public
D1.2	Data Management Plan	6	WP1	1 - ÖMKI	Public
D1.3	Data Management Plan v2	36	WP1	1 - ÖMKI	Public
D1.4	LogFrame Methodology Progress Report (1)	19	WP1	1 - ÖMKI	Public
D1.5	LogFrame Methodology Progress Report (2)	36	WP1	1 - ÖMKI	Public
D2.1	BIOEAST HUB Handbook	6	WP2	18 - EFI	Public
D2.2	HUB Terms of References	14	WP2	12 - BME	Public
D2.3	Report on the inter-ministerial discussion	24	WP2	2 - CR HUB	Public
D3.1	Results from multi-dimensional competency and biomass mapping	13	WP3	15 - DBFZ	Public
D3.2	Integrated assessment w/ description of competency and biomass indices	24	WP3	15 - DBFZ	Public
D3.3	Policy recommendations for biomass and competencies	30	WP3	3 - TTK	Public
D4.1	Bioeconomy related innovation ecosystem mapping	12	WP4	4 - AKI	Public
D4.2	Report on BIOEAST OIC design process and implementation	24	WP4	18 - EFI	Public
D4.3	Report on BIOEAST invest pitching events	36	WP4	22 - IBF	Public
D5.1	Ready to use education materials in bioeconomy, needs and gaps	16	WP5	18 - EFI	Public
D5.2	Stakeholder interviews outcomes and peer review report	30	WP5	2 - CR HUB	Public
D5.3	Roadmap for BIOEAST UniNeT Progress Report	20	WP5	2 - CR HUB	Public
D5.4	Roadmap for BIOEAST UniNeT Final Report	36	WP5	2 - CR HUB	Public
D6.1	7 updated thematic SRIAs	36	WP6	3 - TTK	Public
D6.2	Updates BIOEAST SRIA	36	WP6	3 - TTK	Public
D6.3	7 issue papers and policy briefs	36	WP6	4 - AKI	Public
D6.4	HUB and TWG Evaluation Report	36	WP6	1 - ÖMKI	Sensitive
D7.1	AP methodology	12	WP7	16 - 4CF	Public
D7.2	Final Action Plans	30	WP7	3 - TTK	Public
D8.1	Communication & dissemination and exploitation strategy	6	WP8	17 - APRE	Public
D8.2	Communication & dissemination and exploitation Activities Report	17	WP8	17 - APRE	Public
D8.3	Communication & dissemination and exploitation Activities Final Report	36	WP8	17 - APRE	Public
D8.4	Policy brief about priorities toward the bioeconomy transition in BIOEAST	35	WP8	15 - DBFZ	Public
D9.1	OEI - Requirement No. 1	5	WP9	1 - ÖMKI	Sensitive

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